

The Effect of *Edukasi Terpadu Cegah Stunting* (SIDUCETING) On Knowledge and Attitude Community Health Volunteers at Puskesmas Kubu II, Kubu District, Karangasem Regency, Bali

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Abstract

Introduction: Information on how to stop stunting must be made available as part of efforts to eliminate it. Researchers created *Edukasi Terpadu Cegah Stunting* (SIDUCETING) to improve Community Health Volunteers' (CHVs') attitudes and knowledge about avoiding childhood stunting. **Purpose:** To ascertain how SIDUCETING affects CHVs' knowledge and attitudes regarding preventing stunting. **Methods:** The study employed a quasi-experimental design with a control group and included pre-tests and post-tests. Cluster sampling was used to collect data from a total of 33 respondents, of which 17 were intervention participants and 16 were control participants. The SIDUCETING activity was done by the intervention group, while no therapy was given to the control group. A knowledge and attitude survey is the measuring tool. Wilcoxon, Mann-Whitney U., and Paired T-Test were employed in the data analysis. **Results:** The median value of the group before being given SIDUCETING was in the low knowledge category and the attitude was less supportive. After being given the intervention, the median value of the respondents' knowledge and attitudes increased with the categories of knowledge and supportive attitudes. The control group is still in the category of low knowledge and less supportive attitudes. The results of hypothesis testing using the median difference value show that knowledge has a small effect size = 0.22 and attitude with a moderate effect size = 0.75. **Conclusion:** SIDUCETING can significantly increase the knowledge and attitudes of CHVs regarding prevention of stunting.

Keywords: Community Health Volunteers, Knowledge, Attitude, Health Education

INTRODUCTION

The most important system in improving the level of health is the healthcare delivery system. Therefore, efforts to improve the quality of services are essential and are part of the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) for 2015-2019. Currently, the program faces challenges, one of which is that healthcare services have not yet fully covered the population, particularly in remote and island regions. Another unresolved issue according to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) is the reduction of stunting prevalence in children under five ⁽¹⁾.

Indonesia ranks fifth globally and second in Southeast Asia, after Cambodia, for the prevalence of stunting⁽²⁾. This data is further supported by the 2018 Basic Health Research Report, which indicates a stunting rate of 30.8% among children under five, though this has decreased from 37.2% in 2013. Despite this reduction, the rate in Indonesia remains high, prompting the government to commit to reducing the stunting rate to 19% by 2024 through the RPJMN IV 2020-2024. The province of Bali, which has the lowest stunting prevalence in Indonesia, still has districts where the prevalence exceeds the WHO's (World Health Organization)

recommended maximum of 20%, such as Karangasem District with a prevalence of 22.9% (3).

The Indonesian government has implemented several programs aimed at reducing stunting and ensuring the achievement of its reduction target, including increasing interventions related to sensitive and specific nutrition, providing early detection and stimulation kits for growth and development (SDIDTK), funding childbirth, promoting clean and healthy living behaviors (PHBS), and conducting maternal health education classes. However, these efforts have yet to be implemented on a large scale (4;5).

One approach to reducing stunting is through early prevention. The most critical procedure in prevention is regular screening and follow-up of children's growth. According to Setyowati and Astuti (2015), a strategic effort to detect early growth disorders in children is by monitoring growth charts at integrated health service posts (posyandu). This aligns with the definition of posyandu, which refers to activities carried out by and for the community, targeting children under five, pregnant women, breastfeeding mothers, and women of reproductive age, with health cadres serving as the main implementers.

Health cadres are selected to address individual and community health issues and work closely with primary healthcare services (6). Empowering cadres to increase the coverage of health programs has been outlined in the General Guidelines for Posyandu Management, which includes growth monitoring for children to prevent growth disorders such as stunting (7). The Ministry of Health has received feedback from 178 countries that have identified several conceptual issues with health cadres concerning the Growth Monitoring Program (GMP), including difficulties interpreting growth curves (48%), inaccurate anthropometric data

(40%), and poor understanding of growth curves (29%) (8). Based on this data, it is evident that health cadres require adequate knowledge to properly implement the knowledge they have acquired.

Knowledge plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's actions (overt behavior) (9). Health knowledge does not directly influence behavior; rather, attitudes serve as an intermediary step between knowledge and behavior. Health knowledge acquired through education influences attitudes, which ultimately determine the actions taken. Attitude, as defined, is an evaluative reaction, either favorable or unfavorable, towards something, as expressed through beliefs (10).

The researcher conducted interviews with several health cadres working in the Kubu II Health Center service area regarding their knowledge and attitudes towards stunting. The results of interviews with five cadres revealed that they lacked sufficient knowledge on stunting prevention. Additionally, cadres rarely measured children's height or length, typically only recording weight measurements. They also reported not knowing how to interpret the results of the measurements, as their role was limited to recording the data. Several programs implemented by the local government have primarily been educational, such as sanitation and maternal nutrition counseling. Follow-up knowledge assessments for cadres only occur when they participate in village health competitions.

Currently, there is a lack of research specifically addressing cadres' knowledge of stunting, although studies on cadres' knowledge regarding child growth detection do exist. Data from a study on early childhood growth detection training for posyandu cadres at Puskesmas in Magelang City revealed that 52% of cadres were unable to weigh children correctly, 44% could not properly

complete the Child Health Card (KMS), and 78% were unable to detect developmental issues accurately (11).

Other studies also indicate that some cadres face difficulties interpreting growth charts. A study conducted in South Africa found that more than half of the health cadres were unable to interpret growth curves correctly and lacked the ability to explain the potential causes of stunting (12). This is attributed to the insufficient provision of intensive and ongoing education for health cadres. Another study indicated that when cadres lack knowledge about early childhood development, they are unable to conduct early detection or report to healthcare professionals, resulting in delayed growth and development that cannot be addressed promptly, putting children at risk of developmental delays (13).

In addition to knowledge, studies on cadres' attitudes have also been conducted, one of which (8) revealed that poor attitudes among health cadres can negatively impact children's health and growth. The study found that cadres sometimes fail to monitor children or individuals in growth surveillance, and growth monitoring is not used as an educational tool to promote action to parents for improving child growth. Based on these studies, it can be concluded that many cadres still lack sufficient knowledge and attitudes regarding child growth and development, particularly in growth monitoring. To support the government's efforts to reduce stunting in Indonesia, the researcher conducted a study on Integrated Education for Stunting Prevention (SIDUCETING). The integrated education combines stunting education with the Community-Based Total Sanitation (STBM) program. Another study also explained that stunting is closely related to poor sanitation practices, inadequate water supply, food insecurity, and low levels of parenting education (14).

SIDUCETING represents a novel approach in providing health education by involving cadres as the main actors in stunting prevention. The advantage of SIDUCETING is that cadres are equipped with information and education using easy-to-understand learning methods, including role-play videos and demonstration activities. These methods enable cadres to conduct stunting screening combined with STBM materials on growth monitoring, nutrition intake, and sanitation. Furthermore, cadres are trained on how to measure children's height and interpret the results on a growth curve. It is expected that SIDUCETING will improve cadres' knowledge and attitudes in detecting and preventing stunting in the Kubu II Health Center service area, Karangasem Regency.

METHODS

This study employs a quasi-experiment design with a pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design to examine the impact of the Integrated Education to Prevent Stunting (SIDUCETING) on the knowledge and attitudes of healthcare cadres at Kubu II Health Center, Kubu District, Karangasem Regency. The research model involves providing the SIDUCETING program using a module developed by the researcher and the team to improve cadres' knowledge and attitudes regarding stunting prevention. Pretest assessments were conducted before the intervention, while posttest evaluations were carried out after the education sessions concluded.

The study was conducted in the service area of Kubu II Health Center from July 7 to July 23, 2022. The population consisted of all active healthcare cadres in the working area of Kubu II Health Center in 2022, totaling 78 individuals. The sampling technique used was probability sampling with a one-stage cluster sampling method. The inclusion criteria were healthcare cadres under 50 years of

age who could read and write and had been active in posyandu (integrated health posts) activities over the past year. The final sample size was 17 participants, including a 10% buffer for loss to follow-up, for both the intervention and control groups.

The instruments used to collect data were questionnaires designed to assess the changes in the healthcare cadres' knowledge about stunting prevention. The questionnaire covered three main domains: stunting, Community-Based Total Sanitation (STBM), and the prevention of stunting using the STBM concept. The knowledge questionnaire had undergone validity and reliability testing, with a calculated r-value lower than the critical r-value (0.361). The attitude questionnaire, adapted from Kharyati's (2015) study and modified by the researcher, was also validated, with the same validity threshold ($r < 0.361$). The reliability of the questionnaires was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding reliability scores of 0.850 for knowledge and 0.880 for attitudes.

The SIDUCETING module, developed by the researcher, consists of three components: stunting (definition, causes, and prevention), Community-Based Total Sanitation (STBM) (definition and objectives), and stunting prevention with an STBM approach (monitoring growth, nutrition intake, and sanitation). The cadres were gathered at

the village office hall for the informed consent process and to administer the pretest to those who agreed to participate. The cadres completed the questionnaire independently, with an estimated completion time of approximately 30 minutes.

The SIDUCETING program was conducted at the Village Office Hall in Tianyar, utilizing several teaching methods, including lectures, brainstorming sessions, discussions, Q&A, demonstrations, and re-demonstrations. One participant from the control group dropped out during the study due to illness and was unable to complete the posttest. Consequently, the analyzed data included 33 participants, comprising 17 from the intervention group and 16 from the control group. After completing SIDUCETING, the posttest was administered.

RESULTS

Differences in Knowledge and Attitudes of Healthcare Cadres Before and After the Intervention in the Intervention and Control Groups

The purpose of this analysis is to examine the differences in the increase in knowledge and attitudes of healthcare cadres in preventing stunting before and after the intervention. This is based on the comparison of pretest and posttest results in the intervention and control groups, as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Differences in Knowledge and Attitudes of Cadres Before and After the Intervention in the Intervention and Control Groups

Variable	Intervention (n=17)		p	Control (n=16)		p
	Pretest	Post test		Pretest	Post test	
	Median (IQR Q1-Q3)	Median (IQR Q1-Q3)		Median (IQR Q1-Q3)	Median (IQR Q1-Q3)	
Knowledge	10 (9-11)	18 (17-18)	<0,001 ^a	9 (9-10)	10 (9-10)	0,324 ^a
Attitude	42 (39-43)	54 (52-55)	<0,001 ^b	41 (39-43)	42 (40-43)	0,564 ^b

Note: p-values are derived from (a) Wilcoxon tests and (b) paired t-tests. Significance is considered at $p < 0.05$.

The data analysis results demonstrate a significant difference after the intervention using SIDUCETING, with p-values below 0.05. Although there were increases in median knowledge and attitude scores in the control group, the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

The Effect of SIDUCETING on Healthcare Cadres' Knowledge and Attitudes Toward Stunting Prevention

The impact was measured based on effect size, calculated from the differences in median scores for knowledge and attitudes before and after the intervention in both the control and intervention groups, as shown in the following table:

Table 2. The Effect Size of SIDUCETING on the Knowledge and Attitudes of Cadres in Preventing Stunting

Groups				
	Intervention (n=17)	Control (n=16)	<i>P</i>	<i>d</i>
	Interquartile range (IQR Q1-Q3)	Interquartile range (IQR Q1-Q3)		
Knowledge	8,00 (7-9)	0,00 ((-1)-1)	<0,001	0,22
Attitude	11,00 (6-20)	1,00 ((-1)-1)	<0,001	0,75

Note: n: sample; min: minimum; maks: maximum; p: significance $p < 0.05$; analysis using Mann-Whitney

Based on the table above, the effect size for knowledge is 0.22, which is clinically considered small, while the effect size for attitude is 0.75, which is considered moderate. These results suggest that the Integrated Education to Prevent Stunting (SIDUCETING) had a significant impact on improving the knowledge and attitudes of healthcare cadres at Kubu II Health Center in Karangasem Regency.

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of the healthcare cadres in the intervention group improved positively after receiving the SIDUCETING program, as indicated by the initial pretest median score of 10, which increased to a median score of 18 in the post-test. Meanwhile, in the control group, where no intervention was provided during the study period, the respondents' knowledge did not experience a significant improvement, with a pretest score of 9 and a post-test median score of 10. The education provided through the intervention increased the respondents' ability to answer the material that had been given (15). This is consistent with the study

conducted by (16) on the level of knowledge of healthcare cadres in Cendana Village, Purbalingga, which showed that the average knowledge score of cadres increased by 25.73% from the initial average knowledge score after being given education.

One study related to stunting prevention is GASTIZI 1000, which improved the knowledge capacity of healthcare cadres at the posyandu (17). This study provided education to cadres about stunting, the importance of nutrition during the first 1,000 days of life, and training on monitoring nutritional status using the growth monitoring tool provided by the Ministry of Health to detect stunting. Another study on stunting prevention involved educating mothers of stunted children using brainstorming and audiovisual methods. The results of this study showed an increase in mothers' knowledge scores regarding stunting management (18). The basic concept derived from previous studies shares similarities with SIDUCETING; however, the advantage of this study lies in combining stunting education with the STBM-Stunting concept, which includes

materials on growth monitoring, nutritional intake, and sanitation. The methods used were diverse and varied, such as lectures, discussions, and learning media like videos and posters, all integrated into one educational concept. This made SIDUCETING easier to implement for improving knowledge and attitudes. In the process of reducing stunting, the cadres were taught how to measure children's height through demonstrations conducted by the researcher during the educational sessions, using the growth chart, interpreting WHO growth curves, and practicing proper handwashing techniques. Demonstrations are also an advantage of SIDUCETING because the cadres were taught to implement the lessons they received. According to (19), demonstrations are one of the learning methods that use repetitive movements to learn new processes, such as measuring a child's height or length, which is done monthly, making it easier for the cadres to apply the lessons learned previously. Demonstrations as part of education have a 90% retention rate, improving respondents' understanding of the material (20). The increase in knowledge can also be attributed to the abundance of information provided through educational materials, posters, and videos during the intervention (21).

The attitude of the cadres in the intervention group improved positively after receiving the SIDUCETING program, with the pretest median score of 42 increasing to 54 in the post-test. This change in attitude is also related to the educational delivery process, which means that SIDUCETING improved the cadres' positive attitudes toward stunting prevention. In other words, the cadres were able to understand the messages delivered through the education. This aligns with a study by (12), which found that providing education to cadres on the Growth Monitoring Program (GMP) resulted in a positive improvement in the

cadres' attitudes after the education. A study by (22) states that education, by paying attention to the type of message conveyed, can strengthen the importance of an intervention. Assessing the quality of educational messages and delivery strategies is challenging, but generally, interventions with good quality will improve respondents' understanding and positive attitudes.

The median differences in knowledge and attitude scores between the intervention and control groups indicate that the SIDUCETING program produced significant differences. The effect size shown in Table 2 reveals that although the variables of knowledge and attitude had significant results, the effect size for knowledge was small, while the effect size for attitude was moderate. The researcher explains that the small effect size for knowledge might be due to the expectation that the cadres should already perform their roles well, but they are not required to have sufficient knowledge and skills in health to carry out their duties.

According to (20), education is considered a tool that can be used to enhance knowledge in the health field. A well-conducted educational process will improve health awareness. SIDUCETING had a significant impact on the knowledge and attitudes of cadres in the Kubu II Health Center area. Feedback from respondents indicated that SIDUCETING was very beneficial for the cadres, as the lessons learned were closely related to the activities they performed during posyandu sessions. The increase in knowledge and attitude was due to the education provided using two-way communication, reinforced by educators delivering the material through engaging media, which encouraged the cadres to ask questions and respond to the material (23).

According to (24), although health education has been proven effective in improving the knowledge and attitudes of cadres, it may not be sufficient to enhance

their actual performance, as many other factors influence this. The quality of cadre-based interventions depends not only on proper education but also on supportive supervision and effective coordination within primary care services. Moreover, complex systemic issues, including the roles cadres attribute to themselves and their status compared to other healthcare professionals and the community, may pose significant barriers on the demand side. Socially determined factors may hinder the impact of improved cadre performance on family practices. Therefore, continuous supervision and guidance from healthcare professionals are needed to ensure that the knowledge and attitudes of cadres are not only derived from the interventions they receive.

CONCLUSION

The knowledge of respondents in both groups before receiving SIDUCETING was categorized as low, and their attitudes were considered unsupportive. After receiving SIDUCETING, the knowledge of respondents in the intervention group improved to a good level, while the control group remained in the low category. As for the attitude variable, the control group remained in the unsupportive category after the intervention. Therefore, SIDUCETING was able to significantly improve the knowledge and attitudes of healthcare cadres regarding stunting prevention.

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